

27 and 50%, after 4- and 9- years over the initial level, respectively. The oxidizable carbon and
28 total organic carbon was increased by ~76%, 69% and 64% in Sc4, Sc3 and Sc2, respectively
29 over initial values at 0-15 cm soil depth. Results showed that CA based rice-wheat-mungbean
30 system had more reclamation potential over other studied systems. Therefore, long-term CA
31 practices involving zero tillage with crop residue recycling and efficient crop rotations has
32 the potential to reduce the sodicity stress and improve soil organic carbon thereby bringing
33 the sodic lands under productive crop cultivation.

34 **Keywords:** Sodicity, Conservation agriculture, Long-term experiment, Zero tillage, Soil
35 carbon pools

36 **Introduction**

37 Soil salinity and sodicity is one of the major and prevalent challenges in the current era that
38 hampers global food security and environmental sustainability in the arid and semi-arid
39 regions of the world and adversely affects the global agricultural production and biodiversity.
40 Globally, more than 900 M ha of land, accounting for nearly 20% of the total agricultural
41 land and 33% of the irrigated agricultural lands is affected by salinity (Srivastava and Kumar,
42 2015). The salt stress in soil is becoming prominent due to the ever-increasing global
43 population pressure (projected to be 9.3 billion by 2050), anthropogenic activities (e.g.,
44 intensive cultivation, over-application of groundwater and synthetic fertilizers) and climate
45 change over decades (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2020). About 40-60% of world's salt-affected
46 lands are saline and sodic in nature (Tanji, 1990). In India, total salt affected area is 6.74 M
47 ha out of which approximately 2.95 and 3.79 million hectares area is covered by saline and
48 sodic soils, respectively (Sharma et al. 2015). Sodic soils are characterized by high pH (>8.5),
49 high ESP (>15%) and low salt concentration EC (<4.0 dS/m). In India, annual losses of INR
50 230 billion occur due to the adverse effect of salinity/sodicity on crop growth and
51 productivity (Sharma et al. 2015). This is likely to increase manifold by 2050 with projected

52 increase in salt-affected soils to 16.2 million ha (CSSRI Vision 2050). In India, population is
53 increasing day-by-day and to feed this huge (1.67 billion by 2050) population, salt-affected
54 soils should be reclaimed and brought under productive cultivation. Moreover, at current time
55 climate change together with soil salinity/sodicity will considerably affect the crop
56 productivity (Datta et al., 2017a).

57 Conservation agriculture (CA), having three principles of minimum soil disturbance, crop
58 rotation and soil cover, is endorsed as a practice for sustainable crop production that
59 simultaneously conserves soil and water resources while reducing input costs (Margenot et
60 al., 2017; Jat et al., 2021). The application of CA practices enhances soil quality by reducing
61 the breakdown of soil aggregates, enhancing the infiltration rate, nutrient cycling and soil
62 organic carbon (SOC), which improves soil physical and biochemical properties while
63 reducing soil erosion (Zhang et al., 2018; Jat et al., 2018; 2019a,b; 2020c). CA practices also
64 have higher energy-use efficiency compared to conventional tillage (CT) (Rusu 2014; Jat et
65 al., 2020b). The increase in SOC and aggregate stability under CA plays important role in
66 regulating movement of water and gas, and nutrient cycling (Liu et al., 2015). It is also
67 reported that CA practices improves nutrient availability and soil fertility (Choudhary et al.,
68 2018a, b; Dang et al. 2015). Consequently, increase levels of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P)
69 and potassium (K) were found in the surface layer under CA compared to CT treatment
70 (Martínez et al., 2016). Recently, CA is gaining momentum because of saving in labor, water,
71 and energy with higher systems' productivity and profitability (Jat et al., 2020a, 2019a, b).
72 CA also showed promise in improving soil quality and savings of fertilizer nutrients in
73 reclaimed alkali soils (Jat et al., 2018, 2019a, b; Choudhary et al., 2018a, b, 2020).

74 Reclamation of sodic soils is mostly done by chemical amendments such as gypsum which
75 supplies Ca^{2+} thereby replacing Na^+ from clay exchange complex leading to lower soil pH
76 and ESP. In arid and semiarid regions, sodic soils mostly contain ample amount of native

77 CaCO₃ which serves as a potential Ca²⁺ source but its lower solubility makes it difficult for
78 reclamation of sodic soils. Soil pH, partial pressure of CO₂ and its hydrolysis reaction in soil
79 solution control the CaCO₃ dissolution rate in soil (Plummer et al., 1978). Several researchers
80 have shown that growing trees or crops has the potential in reclaiming calcareous sodic soils
81 with or without chemical amendments application (Chorom and Rengasamy, 1997; Garg,
82 2000; Qadir and Oster, 2002; Mishra et al., 2004; Qadir et al., 2006; Dagar et al. 2001; Dagar
83 and Tomar, 2002; Singh, 2009; Dagar et al., 2014; Dagar and Minhas, 2016; Dagar et al.,
84 2016). In sodic soils, application of organic material significantly increased the partial
85 pressure of CO₂ in to the root zone which leads to production of carbonic acid and helped in
86 dissolution of native CaCO₃ and supplied Ca²⁺ to soil solution (Tan, 1994; Fahu and Keren,
87 2009; Amini et al., 2016; Noori et al., 2021). In an extensive review, Leogrande and Vitti
88 (2018) emphasized the important role of organic matter in improving the quality of salt
89 affected soils by supplying cations and improving soil structure. Organic substances upon
90 decomposition produce organic acids (Trivedi et al., 2017) thereby help in calcite dissolution
91 and reduce soil pH by supplying Ca²⁺ to soil solution (Filho et al. 2020; Papagar et al. 2012).

92 There is hardly any study on how CA mediates soil sodicity through zero tillage (ZT) and
93 crop residue recycling. There is speculation that higher crop residues have the potential to
94 reduce the soil pH in long term. Upon decomposition, crop residues produce organic acids
95 and subsequently H⁺ ions and thereby reduce soil pH. Another possible hypothesis is through
96 the dissolution of CaCO₃ mediated by organic acids that produced during crop residue
97 decomposition (Fig. 1). Therefore, we hypothesize that long-term CA based management
98 practices with diverse crop rotation significantly reduce soil pH through higher organic
99 matter build up in soil. The objectives were i) to study the soil salinity and sodicity
100 parameters under CA practices, ii) to evaluate different SOC pools under long-term CA
101 managements.

102 **Materials and Methods**

103 *Site description*

104 A field experiment was started in the year 2009-10 at ICAR-CSSRI (Indian Council of
105 Agricultural Research-Central Soil Salinity Research Institute) Karnal, India (29°42'20.7" N
106 latitude, 76°57'19.79" E longitude) at an elevation of 243 m above msl (Fig. 2). The region
107 has a semi-arid and subtropical climate, with hot and dry spell in April to June to wet summer
108 spell in July to September and a cool and dry winter spell in October to March. The mean
109 maximum temperature was 31.68°C during month of June, whereas minimum temperature
110 was 11.62°C in coldest month of January. Average rainfall of the area is 670 mm, 75-80% of
111 which occurred during monsoon season. The soil was highly sodic during 1970s with high
112 pH (pH 10.3 in 1:2.5) and exchangeable sodium percentage (97% at 0–5 cm depth) (Bhumbla
113 et al. 1973). After establishment of ICAR-CSSRI, the soils were reclaimed through gypsum
114 application and later on cultivation of crops started (Datta et al. 2015). The soil of the
115 experimental field was silty loam in texture (sand- 34%, silt- 46% and clay- 20%), low in
116 Walkley and Black organic carbon (0.45%) with alkaline pH (ranging from 7.5 to 9.5).

117

118 *Experimental details*

119 In this study, the treatments are termed as scenarios (Sc), which were designed to address
120 various drivers of current as well as future agricultural production system in western Indo-
121 Gangetic plains (IGP) of India. Four scenarios with diversified cereal based cropping system,
122 tillage and crop establishment, residue management, and water and nutrient management
123 were evaluated. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design (RBD) with three
124 replications in production-scale plots (2000 m²; 20 m × 100 m). The Scenarios included: Sc1-
125 conventional tilled transplanted rice-conventional tilled wheat (CT-RW) called farmer's
126 practice; Sc2- conventional tilled transplanted rice – zero till wheat-mungbean (CTR-

127 ZTWMB); Sc3- zero tilled rice-wheat-mungbean (ZT-RWMB) and Sc4- zero tilled maize-
128 wheat-mungbean (ZT-MWMB). The details of the treatments along with management
129 practices were given in Supp. Table 1. The best crop management practices for nutrient,
130 weed, pest was followed in all scenarios except Sc1, where farmers' practices were followed.

131

132 *Crop managements (crop establishment method, planting, fertilization etc.)*

133 In Sc1, rice was grown by performing two harrowing plus two cultivator operation followed
134 by wooden planking in dry tillage, where as puddling was done by passing two harrowing
135 followed by one time planking. Rice seedlings (20-25 days old) were transplanted manually
136 in main field after puddling. In CT-wheat, field was prepared by passing two harrowing and
137 two cultivator operation. Wheat seeds were manually broadcasted in the soil followed by
138 harrowing and planking. In Sc2, rice was transplanted in main field after puddling and field
139 preparatory dry tillage was performed by three harrowing and one planking operation. The
140 zero tillage (ZT) rice (direct seeded rice; DSR), wheat, mungbean and maize were planted by
141 'Happy Seeder' machine in all CA based scenarios (Sc2, Sc3, and Sc4). The distance
142 between rows was maintained at 22.5 cm for ZT- rice, wheat and mungbean, where as for
143 maize row to row distance was maintained at 67.5 cm. Both rice and maize were sown during
144 June before onset of monsoon season, wheat was sown in between last week of October to
145 first week of November and mungbean was cultivated in between April to mid June (between
146 wheat harvesting and rice sowing) of every year. The best management practices were
147 followed with the standard seed rates in all crops.

148 Recommended doses of fertilizers (150-60-60 kg ha⁻¹ of N-P₂O₅-K₂O for both rice and wheat)
149 were applied in all CA based scenarios (Sc2 – Sc4). In Sc1, farmers' practice was followed as
150 practiced with higher N (175 kg N ha⁻¹), medium P (46 kg ha⁻¹) and no K fertilizer in the plot.
151 The nutrient N was supplied mainly through urea (46% N), however P and K were supplied

152 through DAP (di-ammonium phosphate) (18:46:00) and MoP (muriate of potash- 60% K₂O),
153 respectively. NPK complex fertilizer (12:32:16) was also used in different scenarios as per
154 recommended dose. In all the scenarios, P and K along with ~17% N were applied as basal
155 and remaining N was supplied by urea as top dressing in three equal splits. In mungbean, no
156 fertilizer was given in Sc2-Sc4.

157 *Residue management*

158 In Sc1, 100% rice and wheat residues were removed from field. In Sc2, 100% rice and 30%
159 wheat residues (anchored wheat stubbles of 20-25 cm height) was kept and 100% mungbean
160 residues was incorporated during puddling operation in rice. In Sc3, 100% rice and
161 mungbean and 30% wheat residues was kept on surface. But in Sc4, 65% (anchored stubbles
162 up to cob position) maize, 30% wheat and 100% mungbean residues were kept on soil
163 surface. During the experimental period, about 159 Mg ha⁻¹ crop residues (including maize,
164 wheat and mungbean) were recycled in Sc4 whereas in Sc2 and Sc3 about 153 and 139 t ha⁻¹
165 crop residues (including rice, wheat and mungbean), respectively were recycled (Suppl. Table
166 2). For rice and wheat residue, carbon (C) input was calculated assuming a concentration of
167 0.45 kg C per kg dry matter (Johnson et al., 2006) and for maize residue, 0.40 kg C per kg
168 dry matter (Sawyer and Mallarino, 2007) and for mungbean residue, 0.44 kg C per kg dry
169 matter (Zang et al. 2015). During the experimental period, in Sc2, 41.9, 10.9 and 15.5 t C ha⁻¹
170 was added through rice, wheat and mungbean crop residues, respectively. Whereas in Sc3
171 and Sc4, it was 37.1, 10.2, 14.8 and 40.5, 10.7 and 14.8 t C ha⁻¹ through rice/maize, wheat
172 and mungbean, respectively were recycled.

173

174 *Soil sample collection and analysis*

175 In the year 2009-10, rice was grown as uniformity crop and for maintaining the residues. Soil
176 samples were collected after harvesting of common crop wheat in all the scenarios during the

177 year 2010 (initial level), 2014 (after 4- years) and 2019 (after 9- years) from 0-15 and 15-30
178 cm soil depths using auger with 5 cm internal diameter. The said experiment was started on
179 the partially reclaimed sodic soils where sodic patches were prevailed with varied pH ranging
180 from 7.5 to 9.5. During the wheat season 2009-10, the sodic spots were identified by
181 observing the patchy growth of the wheat crop (peculiar symptoms of sodic condition) and
182 confirmed by measuring the pH and ESP in each plot. A sizable area (size: ~25 m²) was
183 earmarked in each plots as per the soil pH. Within each plot, sub-samples were collected
184 from three locations for each pH range and then a composite sample was prepared of each
185 depth. Part of the soil samples were air-dried in shade, ground to pass through a 2-mm sieve,
186 and stored in plastic containers for analysis of selected soil chemical properties.

187 Soil pH₂ (soil: water 1:2 ratio) and pHs in aqueous paste of the soil and water were
188 determined by using digital pH meter (USSL, 1954). Electrical conductivity of soil
189 suspension (soil: water 1:2 ratio) (EC₂) and saturation extract of soil paste (EC_e) were
190 measured using EC meter (USSL, 1954). Sodium and potassium concentration were
191 determined in soil saturation extract by flame photometer (USSL, 1954; Bhargava, 2003).
192 Calcium and Magnesium concentration were estimated by EDTA method (Schwartzbach et
193 al., 1946). Carbonate and bicarbonate were determined by titrating the sample against
194 standard acid. Chloride was determined by titrating the soil extract against silver nitrate
195 solution using potassium chromate as an indicator (USSL, 1954) and sulphate was estimated
196 by turbidimetric method (Chesnin and Yien, 1951). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) and
197 exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) of soils were determined by the method of Tucker
198 (1985). Sodium adsorption ratio (SAR_e) of soil saturation extract was calculated by following
199 equation

$$SAR = \frac{[Na^+]}{\sqrt{\frac{([Ca^{2+}] + [Mg^{2+}])}{2}}}$$

200

201 Where, $[Na^+]$ represents the concentration of cation in $cmol (p+)L^{-1}$ note halving sum of
 202 $[Ca^{2+}]$ and $[Mg^{2+}]$ before taking square root.

203 The oxidizable organic carbon (OC) was determined following wet oxidation method of
 204 Walkley and Black method (1934). Very labile carbon (VLC) was measured following Datta
 205 et al. (2017b) using 12N H_2SO_4 . Total carbon (TC) was measured using Elementer CN
 206 analyser (Elementer Vario EL Cube). The $CaCO_3$ content of the soils was measured
 207 following Collins Calcimeter (Alison and Moodie, 1965). Inorganic carbon (IC) was
 208 calculated from $CaCO_3$ content by multiplying 0.12 on mass basis. Total organic carbon
 209 (TOC) was calculated by subtracting inorganic carbon from total carbon.

210 *Statistical analysis*

211 Data analysis was done with the help of SAS 9.1 software (SAS Institute, 2001). The
 212 treatment means were compared by least significant difference (LSD) test at $P = 0.05$ (Gomez
 213 and Gomez, 1984). A Pearson's correlation matrix was constructed among the soil properties
 214 studied to determine the common relationships between parameters.

215

216 **Results**

217 **Changes in soil pH and EC (electrical conductivity)**

218 CA based scenarios showed significant decline in soil pH_2 (soil:water; 1:2) with the
 219 increasing years of managements at 0-15 cm soil depth (Table 1). Lowest decline in pH_2
 220 (6.98) was observed in Sc2 at 0-15 cm soil depth among the scenarios. At 0-15 cm soil depth,
 221 about 8% decline in soil pH_2 after 4- years (year 2014) and 18% decline after 9- years (year
 222 2019) was observed in Sc2 over 2010 level (8.53, initial level). In Sc3, about 8% and 14%

223 decline in soil pH₂ was observed after 4- and 9- years, respectively compared to initial level (
224 year 2010) whereas, in Sc4, decline in soil pH₂ was 4.5% and 12%. At 15-30 cm soil depth,
225 highest decline in soil pH₂ was observed in Sc2 (15.5%) closely followed by Sc4 (14%) after
226 9- years (year 2019) over the initial level. Similar observation was also observed in pHs
227 under different scenarios. Lowest pHs was observed in Sc2 (6.37) whereas conventional
228 management did not exert any significant effect on soil pH reduction (Table 1).

229 Significant variation in EC (EC₂ and ECe) was observed across the years although the values
230 are much lower than the critical level of 4.0 dS m⁻¹ above which significant impact on plant
231 growth manifested (Table 2). With progress in cultivation practices, EC₂ decreased (about
232 28%) significantly after 9- years, lowest being associated with Sc2 (0.34 dS m⁻¹) and Sc3
233 (0.33 dS m⁻¹) at 0-15 cm soil depth. However, ~33% decline in EC₂ was observed in Sc3 at
234 15-30 cm soil depth. Similar observation was also observed in ECe across the years. In the
235 first four years, the decline rate of EC was slower (25% of total reduction) and after that the
236 rate was increased exponentially in last 5 years (75% of total). At 15-30 cm soil depth, about
237 29% decline in ECe was observed in CA based managements after 9- years over 4- years
238 (Table 2).

239 **Cations and anions**

240 Significant variation in cations was observed among the scenarios except K⁺ ion. With
241 progress in CA based management, extractable Na⁺ ion concentration decreased significantly
242 across the years (Table 3). After 9- years, highest decrease in extractable Na⁺ ion
243 concentration was observed in Sc4 (49.3%) followed by Sc3 (46%) and Sc2 (45%) at 0-15
244 cm soil depth over the initial values. Similarly, at 15-30 cm soil depth, significant decline in
245 extractable Na⁺ was recorded in Sc3 (49%) and Sc2 (47%). Extractable Ca²⁺ concentration
246 decreased across the years with the progress of cultivation practices except Sc3. Highest
247 decrease was observed in Sc1 (19%) followed by Sc2 (8.1%) and Sc4 (5.4%) whereas, Sc3

248 showed reverse trend with 24% higher after 9- years over initial level at 0-15 cm soil depth.
249 Similar trend was also observed at 15-30 cm depth except Sc1 where Ca^{2+} ion concentration
250 increased with years. Extractable Mg^{2+} ion concentration showed significant variation among
251 the scenarios across the years. With progress in cultivation practices, extractable Mg^{2+} ion
252 concentration decreased significantly except Sc1, highest and lowest values were associated
253 with Sc3 (20.2%) and Sc2 (3.3%) at 0-15 cm soil depth after 9- years. In Sc1, about 54%
254 higher extractable Mg^{2+} ion concentration was observed after 9- years at surface soil depth.
255 At 15-30 cm soil depth, Sc3 and Sc4 registered significant decrease in Mg^{2+} ion
256 concentration whereas Sc1 showed significant increase (54%) after 9- years over initial level
257 (Table 3).

258 Extractable anions varied significantly among the scenarios across the years. Except Sc1,
259 extractable carbonate content decreased significantly with progress in CA based
260 managements (Table 4). Sc3 showed 100% decline in CO_3^{2-} content followed by Sc2 (88%)
261 and Sc4 (81%) at 0-15 cm soil depth after 9- years, whereas about 98% increase in Sc1 (1.33
262 me L^{-1}) was observed. At subsurface depth, extractable CO_3^{2-} disappeared in all the scenarios
263 with progress in cultivation. Extractable bicarbonate content exhibited significant decline
264 after 9- years of CA based managements. After 9- years, highest and lowest decline was
265 observed under Sc2 (74%) and Sc4 (66%), respectively at 0-15 cm soil depth over initial
266 level (11.75 and 13.75 me L^{-1} , respectively). Similar observations were also reported at 15-30
267 cm soil depth on average with 50-59% decline in bicarbonate content. CA based
268 managements resulted significant decrease in extractable Cl^- content after 9- years of
269 continuous cultivation. Highest decrease in Cl^- content was observed in Sc2 and Sc4 (~39%)
270 followed by Sc3 (22.5%) whereas conventional system (Sc1) also recorded 19% less Cl^- after
271 9-years over initial (Sc1: 5.54 me L^{-1} , Sc2: 4.81 me L^{-1} , Sc4: 9.24 me L^{-1}) at 0-15 cm soil
272 depth. Significantly lower Cl^- was observed in Sc2 (49%) followed by Sc4 (28%) whereas

273 Sc3 (4%) showed lowest decline in Cl^- at 15-30 cm soil depth after 9- years compared to
274 initial level. On average, partial CA (Sc2) and CT based managements (Sc1) facilitated
275 highest decrease (80%) in extractable SO_4^{2-} concentration at 0-15 cm soil depth after 9- years
276 of cultivation. After 9- years, CA based managements (Sc3 and Sc4) on average resulted 63%
277 and 54% decline in SO_4^{2-} concentration at 0-15 and 15-30 cm soil depth, respectively (Table
278 4).

279 **CEC (cation exchange capacity), ESP (exchangeable sodium percentage) and SAR** 280 **(sodium adsorption ratio)**

281 Long-term CA based practices resulted significant increase in CEC of soil across the years
282 compared to CT based agriculture (Fig. 3). At 0-15 cm soil depth, Sc2 and Sc3 recorded 35%
283 and 38% higher CEC after 4- years and about 89% and 58% higher CEC after 9- years over
284 initial level (CEC of 9.06% and 7.73%). Whereas, after 9- years Sc4 showed 24% higher
285 CEC at 0-15 cm soil depth. At 15-30 cm soil depth, about 21.3% and 21.6%, and 48% and
286 50% higher CEC was observed in Sc2 and Sc3, respectively after 4- and 9- years. Sc4
287 recorded 19% and 30% higher CEC after 4- and 9- years, respectively (Fig. 3).

288 With progress in CA based managements, ESP decreased significantly across the years (Fig.
289 3). Highest and lowest decrease in ESP was 43% and 4% in Sc2 and Sc3 after 4- years and
290 goes up to 50% and 18% after 9- years compared to initial level, respectively. At 15-30 cm
291 soil depth, Sc2 recorded highest decline in ESP after 4- years (49%) and 9- years (60%).
292 Scenario 3 and Sc4 registered 24% and 29% after 4- years and 37% and 32% decrease in ESP
293 after 9- years, respectively (Fig. 3). Across the years of cultivation both CT and CA practices
294 resulted significant decline in SAR at both the soil depths. The decline in SAR was in the
295 order of Sc1>Sc2>Sc3>Sc4 at 0-15 cm soil depth whereas, at 15-30 cm soil depth, the order
296 was Sc1 (55%) >Sc3 (52%) >Sc2 (47%) >Sc1 (17%) after 9- years (Table 5).

297 **CaCO₃ content**

298 Significant variation in CaCO₃ content was observed among the scenarios except Sc4 (Fig.
299 4). After 4- years, similar magnitude of decline in CaCO₃ content was recorded in Sc1 (53%),
300 Sc2 (50%) and Sc3 (50%) at 0-15 cm soil depth. However, after 9- years, highest decline
301 were associated with Sc3 (46%). At 15-30 cm soil depth, after 4- years, Sc3 (41%) and Sc1
302 (38%) recorded significant decline in CaCO₃ content whereas Sc4 showed 25% increase over
303 initials. However, after 9- years significant decline in CaCO₃ content was observed in Sc3
304 (24%) followed by Sc1 (19%) at 15-30 cm soil depth (Fig. 4).

305 **Inorganic carbon (IC)**

306 Significant decline in IC was observed under CA based managements (Fig. 4). After 9- years,
307 at 0-15 cm soil depth, Sc2 registered significant decline (59%) in IC followed by Sc3 (52%)
308 compared to initial values. After 4- years, Sc3 showed 45% decrease in IC content over initial
309 level. In both the years lowest decline was associated with Sc4 (9% and 18%) at surface soil.
310 At 15-30 cm soil, Sc1 recorded highest decline (30%) followed by Sc3 (29%) and Sc2 (14%)
311 after 4- years. In 2019, IC decreased significantly in Sc1 (36%) followed by Sc3 (29%) and
312 Sc4 (19%) whereas Sc2 recorded 27% higher IC at 15-30 cm soil depth compared to initial
313 level (Fig. 4).

314 **Organic carbon pools**

315 **Very labile carbon (VLC)**

316 Year's together practice of CA had resulted significant increase in very labile carbon across
317 the scenarios (Fig. 5). After 9- years, Sc3 recorded, about 175% higher VLC over initial level
318 at 0-15 cm soil depth. Sc1 (114%), Sc2 (59%) and Sc4 (55%) also showed significant
319 increase in VLC over 9- years of continuous cultivation. After 4- years, increase in VLC was
320 in the order of Sc1 (50%) > Sc4 (41%) > Sc3 (31%) > Sc2 (28%) at 0-15 cm soil depth over
321 initial level. At 15-30 cm soil depth, Sc4 showed higher VLC by 24% and 57% after 4- and 9-
322 years, respectively. Sc1 also showed 21% and 26% higher VLC at 15-30 cm soil depth after

323 4- and 9- years. Sc2 and Sc3 showed similar VLC across the scenarios and over the years of
324 cultivation (Fig. 5).

325 **Walkley and Black oxidizable organic carbon (WBC)**

326 After 4- years, significant increase in WBC was observed in CA based scenarios, highest
327 being associated with Sc3 (62%) followed by Sc4 (60%) and Sc1 (52%) at 0-15 cm soil
328 depth. Whereas, after 9- years, Sc4 (76%) showed highest increase in WBC followed by Sc3
329 (69%) and Sc2 (62%). At 15-30 cm soil depth, about 14% decline in WBC was observed in
330 Sc1 after 9- years over initial level of 0.36%. After 9- years, highest increase in WBC was
331 observed in Sc2 (66%) at 15-30 cm soil depth followed by Sc4 (47%) and Sc3 (38%). In
332 2014 also, 14-38% higher WBC was recorded as compared to 2010 irrespective of scenarios
333 (Fig. 5).

334 **Total organic carbon (TOC)**

335 TOC also showed similar trend as WBC among the scenarios across the years (Fig. 6). With
336 progress in cultivation, Sc4 showed higher TOC (77%) followed by Sc3 (69%) and Sc2
337 (65%) at 0-15 cm soil depth after 9-years of experimentation. After 4- years, TOC was 61%
338 higher in Sc4 and Sc3, and 54% in Sc2 over Sc1. At 15-30 cm soil depth, Sc1 registered 13%
339 decline in TOC after 9- years, whereas Sc2 recorded highest TOC (65%) followed by Sc4
340 (46%) and Sc3 (40%). After 4- years, Sc1 showed 39% higher TOC followed by Sc3 (28%),
341 Sc2 (26%) and lowest in Sc4 (13%) over initial level (Fig. 6).

342 **Total carbon (TC)**

343 After 4- years, similar increase in TC was observed in Sc3 (60%) and Sc4 (61%) whereas Sc2
344 registered about 51% increase at 0-15 cm soil depth over initial level (Fig. 6). Whereas, after
345 9- years, Sc4 recorded 74% higher TC followed by Sc3 (63%) and Sc2 (61%) at 0-15 cm soil
346 depth. CT based practices (Sc1) did not show any increase in TC content over the years. At

347 15-30 cm soil depth, Sc2 recorded significantly higher TC (64%) after 9-years followed by
348 Sc4 (44%) and Sc3 (35%), whereas Sc1 showed 15% decline in TC compared to initial level.
349 Whereas, after 4- years, Sc4 and Sc3, recorded 14% and 24% higher TC compared to Sc1.

350 **Interaction effects among the soil parameters**

351 Significant interactions were observed among the scenarios, years and scenarios \times years
352 (Table 6). Extractable Ca^{2+} showed significant effect ($p < 0.001$) of scenarios at 0-15 cm soil
353 depth whereas the scenarios effect on K^+ and Mg^{2+} was significant ($p < 0.001$) at 15-30 cm soil
354 depth (Table 6). Different carbon pools such as VLC, WBC, IC, TOC and TC were
355 significantly influenced by scenarios except at 15-30 cm soil depths for WBC, TOC and TC.
356 CaCO_3 , ESP and pH_2 were significantly influenced ($p < 0.001$) by scenarios at both the soil
357 depths. Different CA based management scenarios significantly influenced EC_2 , EC_e ,
358 extractable Na^+ , CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , VLC, WBC, TOC, IC, TC, CaCO_3 , CEC, ESP, pH_2
359 and pH_s at both the soil depths except IC and CaCO_3 at 15-30 cm soil depth and Cl^- at 0-15
360 cm soil depth. Significant positive interaction was observed for extractable Mg^{2+} , WBC, TOC
361 and TC at 0-15 cm soil depth (Table 6).

362 **Relationships among the soil properties**

363 Pearson's correlations matrix has been constructed among the soil properties studied (Table
364 7). Significant correlations were observed among the soil properties. Soil pH_2 was
365 significantly positively correlated to pH_s , EC_2 , Na^+ , Cl^- , ESP and SAR whereas negatively
366 correlated to Ca^{2+} , CEC, TOC, and VLC. Soil EC_2 was significantly positively correlated to
367 pH_s , EC_e , Na^+ , CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , SAR and negatively correlated to CEC and VLC.
368 EC_e was significantly positively correlated to Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} and
369 negatively correlated to CEC. Extractable Na^+ was significantly positively correlated to CO_3^{2-}
370 , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , ESP, SAR and negatively correlated to CEC and VLC. CEC was

371 significantly positively correlated to TOC and VLC whereas negatively correlated to ESP of
372 soil. TOC was significantly negatively correlated to ESP, SAR and positively correlated to
373 VLC. ESP was significantly negatively correlated to VLC (Table 7).

374 **Discussion**

375 **Changes in soil pH and EC under different CA practices**

376 With progress in CA based managements, soil pH (pH₂ and pH_s) declined significantly which
377 might be due to decomposition of crop residues recycled over the years (Filho et al. 2020).
378 During decomposition of crop residues, partial pressure of CO₂ increased significantly
379 leading to production of carbonic acids which declined soil pH and subsequently enhanced
380 dissolution of native CaCO₃ (Fahu and Keren, 2009; Prapagar et al., 2012). Similar
381 observations were reported under ZT with crop residue retention compared to CT with crop
382 residue removal (Kibet et al., 2016; Gura and Mnkeni, 2019; Mtyobile et al., 2019). Soil pH
383 was lower under CA based management systems, supporting previous studies (Gura and
384 Mnkeni, 2019; Jat et al., 2018). The lower pH in CA might be due to accumulation of soil
385 organic matter (SOM) and soil with crop residue, increasing the number of electrolytes then
386 decreasing pH (Rahman et al., 2008). Inclusion of legume crop (mungbean) between rice and
387 wheat and incorporation of its residues also facilitated reduction in soil pH as reported by
388 many researchers (Dhar et al. 2014; Islam et al. 2019). Higher crop residue retention in CA
389 based managements resulted production of organic acids upon decomposition which diluted
390 salt concentration leading to lower EC in soil (Rahman et al., 2008). SOC also improved the
391 soil physical structure which facilitated the leaching of salts from upper soil layer. Higher
392 decrease in soil pH and EC was recorded with Sc2 compared to other scenarios where
393 residues were incorporated during puddling (churning of soil in presence of water) of soil for
394 rice transplanting. Incorporation hastens the crop residue decomposition process and secretes
395 more organic acids.

396 **Changes in cations and anions, CEC and ESP under different CA practices**

397 Crop residue retention is the main factor of the scenarios to improve CEC in this study. The
398 increase in CEC (Murphy et al., 2016) and Ca^{2+} after the retention of crop residue was
399 previously reported (Mohanty et al., 2015). Although, the increase in availability of Mg and
400 K was reported by Yang et al. (2017) and, Gura and Mnkeni (2019) under No-tillage (NT)
401 with crop residue retention compared to the CT practices but in our study this trend was not
402 observed. Many researchers (Godde et al., 2016; Haruna and Nkongolo, 2020) reported that
403 crop residue retention increases the SOM which is a main factor in the increase of CEC and
404 available Mg, K and Ca. Our study suggests that in marginal soils CEC and Ca^{2+} are also
405 more sensitive towards crop residue retention than Mg^{2+} and K^+ . Organic acids produced
406 upon decomposition of crop residues (Prapagar et al. 2012; Filho et al. 2020) and carbonic
407 acids generated from higher partial pressure of CO_2 during microbial and root respiration had
408 resulted dissolution of native Ca^{2+} from CaCO_3 concretions (Qadir et al., 2005; Fahu and
409 Keren, 2008) which replace the Na^+ from exchange phase and good soil structure facilitated
410 leaching of Na from upper soil layers. As a result, soil ESP also declined under CA based
411 managements over the years. Availability of Na was lower under NT but not at the cost of
412 good crop production than in CT, supporting previous studies (Loke et al., 2014). Good soil
413 structure due to higher SOC content under CA based managements also enhanced the
414 leaching of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} from upper soil layers under CA based managements (Leogrande
415 and Vitti, 2018) which explain the lower concentration in those scenarios. In CA based
416 scenarios (Sc2-Sc4), increased content of SOC facilitated the improved soil structure and
417 physical conditions which facilitated in increasing the CEC and reducing the ESP over the
418 years. Both rice based systems (Sc2 and Sc3) found better with regard to cations and anions
419 as compared to CT based rice (Sc1) and CA based maize system (Sc4).

420 **Variation in SOC pools under different CA practices**

421 Higher very labile carbon in CA based management practices was due to long term crop
422 residue retention at soil surface which upon decomposition release labile carbon to soil. Jat et
423 al. (2019a) also reported higher labile carbon content at surface soil under CA based
424 managements. Higher microbial activity at surface soil under CA based managements also
425 contributed higher production of very labile carbon in those scenarios (Choudhary et al.,
426 2018a, b). Parihar et al. (2018) also reported higher very labile carbon as MBC at surface
427 soils under CA based managements in Northwest India. All CA based managements resulted
428 higher SOC in comparison with CT. The increased SOC is likely related to the redistribution
429 of SOC within aggregates, which increases its stability under CA (Sheehy et al., 2015). The
430 greater soil aggregation would slow down the SOM decomposition rates in CA practices
431 (Sauvadet et al., 2018; Jat et al., 2019b). The improvement of SOC stock in the topsoil (0-15
432 cm) is greater than in the subsoil (15-30 cm) is in line with the positive effects of CA
433 practices on SOC stock being mainly limited to surface soil layers (Badagliacca et al., 2018;
434 Hubbard et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2020). In the subsoil physical accessibility of the organic C
435 to microorganisms was a major control of carbon (C) dynamics (Salome et al., 2010). Higher
436 microflora and fauna resulted in to higher C content in CA based management systems
437 (Choudhary et al., 2018a, b). The results of SOC stock in the subsoil are thus probably due to
438 the reduction of soil disturbance in CA systems, affecting the vertical separation of
439 decomposers and the substrate in the subsoil (Li et al., 2018; Mondal et al., 2020). At the
440 field scale spatial heterogeneity in C content was also greater in the subsoil than in topsoil
441 (Salome et al., 2010). Collectively, as compared to the topsoil, subsoil has less potential in
442 gaining SOC stock with the application of conservation tillage practices (Mondal et al.,
443 2020). The SOC pools under different scenario depend upon the organic residues recycled
444 over the years. Across the soil depth (0-30cm) the SOC content is more or less same under
445 different CA based scenarios but it varied with management (retention vs incorporation) in

446 upper and lower layers. With progress in CA based managements CaCO_3 and inorganic
447 carbon content decreased in soil. . In addition, higher partial pressure of CO_2 due to higher
448 microbial activity and root respiration during decomposition of crop residues facilitated
449 production of carbonic acids which mainly attack native CaCO_3 (Qadir et al. 2005) and
450 causes its dissolution and release Ca^{2+} ions into soil solution (Fahu and Keren, 2008, 2009).
451 As a result CaCO_3 as well as inorganic carbon concentration reduced and soil pH and ESP
452 decreased through natural reclamation of sodic soils. In CA based managements, higher
453 fungal and bacterial population and higher abundance of copiotrophs resulted in to the
454 accelerated crop residue decomposition (Choudhary et al., 2018 a, b, c; 2020). Kim et al.
455 (2020) observed increased CaCO_3 dissolution due to increased soil water storage and
456 transport resulting from agricultural managements such as crop cultivation. The acids
457 released by the microbes helped to the dissolution of CaCO_3 and subsequently lower
458 inorganic carbon (Pal, 2013).

459 **Relationships among the soil properties irrespective of scenarios**

460 Significant relationships were observed among the soil properties irrespective of management
461 scenarios. Higher soil pH was resulted due to higher Na^+ concentration, ESP and SAR
462 thereby explaining positive relations among them whereas higher Ca^{2+} ion reduces the soil
463 pH. The SOC under CA based systems (Sc2-Sc4) showed the negative correlation with ESP
464 and pH. Negative correlation between SOC and soil pH and ESP might be due to higher soil
465 pH and Na^+ ion concentration which results in dispersion of soil due to prevalence of sodium
466 ions thereby favouring oxidation of SOC. The partial CA based rice system (Sc2) recorded
467 the lowest pH and followed by Sc3 and Sc4 and highest with Sc1 (CT system). Incorporation
468 of crop residue lowers down the pH across the profile in Sc2. Li et al. (2020) also observed
469 negative correlation between soil pH and SOC stock in a global meta-analysis to evaluate the
470 effect of crop residue retention and minimum tillage on SOC storage. Chandel et al. (2021)

471 also reported that soil pH and SOC were negatively correlated while studying the effect of
472 saline irrigation water on seed spices. Malobane et al. (2020) reported significant increase in
473 CEC upon 30% crop residue retention in sorghum-based cropping system in marginal soils of
474 South Africa. Higher TOC in soil releases more very labile carbon due to higher microbial
475 activity in CA based managements. Significant correlations between TOC and very labile
476 carbon were observed by Datta et al. (2015) while studying distribution of SOC under
477 different land uses in a reclaimed sodic soil.

478 In our study, different scenario (portfolio of interventions varied in cropping system,
479 tillage, crop establishment, residue management and fertilizer management) were compared
480 to find out the best scenario. Earlier, most of the published work is related to comparison
481 between individual treatments like ZT vs CT and with residue and without residue etc. So, we
482 have evaluated the portfolio of intervention (scenario) in CA based cereal systems of IGP and
483 suggested that CA based rice-wheat–mungbean system has ability to reclaim the sodic soils
484 over a period of time. Thus, farmers of IGP are advocated to adopt the CA based
485 management practices in both normal as well as salt affected soils in their existing rice-wheat
486 system for soil quality restoration.

487

488 **Conclusions**

489 Long-term CA has the potential to reclaim the degraded lands (sodic soils) in intensive cereal
490 based systems of western IGP. The soil organic carbon pools increased significantly due to
491 higher carbon input in the form of crop residues which helped in reducing soil pH. Results
492 showed that partial CA based rice-wheat-mungbean systems (Sc2) found more suitable in
493 reducing the soil pH, EC and ESP, and in improving the cation exchange capacity of sodic
494 soil as compared to other scenarios. The full CA based rice-wheat-mungbean system (Sc3) is

495 more effective in reclamation of sodic soils as compared to maize-wheat-mungbean system
496 (Sc4). In CA systems, ZT with crop residue recycling helped in improving the SOC by ~65-
497 75% over initial values after 9-year of continuous cultivation. So, it is evident that CA based
498 scenarios improved the soil chemical conditions which is required for the good soil health for
499 getting higher yields. Thus, the present findings confirm the benefits of CA in enhancing soil
500 quality in degraded ecosystems. In rice-wheat system of IGP, about 1.8 Mha area is affected
501 by soil sodicity and it can be reclaimed by following the CA based management practices as
502 plenty of crop residues are available freely and may be used for productive purposes.
503 Therefore, CA is an excellent supplement which can be used for the reclamation of
504 calcareous sodic soils to improve the reclamation efficiency and deserves further
505 investigation in highly sodic soils.

506

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815 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2018.02.025>

816 Table 1. Changes in soil pH₂ and pHs under different management scenarios

Scenario/ Year/ Soil depth	pH ₂						pHs					
	2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019	
	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30
Sc1	8.59 ^{Aa}	8.62 ^{Aa}	8.46 ^{Aa}	8.52 ^{Aa}	8.33 ^{Aa}	8.58 ^{Aa}	8.23 ^{Aa}	8.22 ^{Aa}	8.02 ^{Aa}	8.37 ^{Aa}	8.17 ^{Aa}	8.35 ^{Aa}
Sc2	8.53 ^{Aa}	8.68 ^{Aa}	7.84 ^{BCb}	8.16 ^{ABb}	6.98 ^{Cc}	7.33 ^{Cc}	8.13 ^{Aa}	8.08 ^{Aa}	7.59 ^{Bb}	7.99 ^{ABa}	6.37 ^{Cc}	7.20 ^{Bb}
Sc3	8.38 ^{Aa}	8.56 ^{Aa}	7.74 ^{Cb}	8.09 ^{Bb}	7.24 ^{BCc}	7.62 ^{Bc}	8.07 ^{Aa}	8.18 ^{Aa}	7.62 ^{Bb}	7.82 ^{Bab}	6.99 ^{Bc}	7.38 ^{Bb}
Sc4	8.50 ^{Aa}	8.41 ^{Aa}	8.12 ^{Ba}	7.86 ^{Bb}	7.47 ^{Bb}	7.25 ^{Cc}	8.28 ^{Aa}	8.08 ^{Aa}	7.59 ^{Bb}	7.64 ^{Bb}	7.08 ^{Bc}	7.21 ^{Bc}

817 Same upper and lower case letters are not significantly different at P < 0.05 among the scenarios in a column and among the years in rows, respectively according to LSD
 818 Test for separation of mean. Values are the average of three replicates (n = 3)

819

820 Table 2. Changes in soil EC₂ and ECe (dS m⁻¹) under different management scenarios

Scenario/ Year/ Soil depth	EC ₂						ECe					
	2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019	
	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30
Sc1	0.48 ^{Aa}	0.51 ^{Aa}	0.42 ^{Aa}	0.52 ^{Aa}	0.38 ^{Aa}	0.37 ^{Aa}	1.48 ^{Aa}	1.25 ^{Aa}	1.26 ^{Aa}	1.04 ^{Aa}	1.29 ^{Aa}	1.0 ^{Aa}
Sc2	0.45 ^{Aa}	0.43 ^{Aa}	0.48 ^{Aa}	0.43 ^{Aa}	0.34 ^{Aa}	0.30 ^{Aa}	1.38 ^{Aa}	1.04 ^{Aab}	1.23 ^{Aa}	1.28 ^{Aa}	1.05 ^{Aa}	0.83 ^{Ab}
Sc3	0.48 ^{Aa}	0.42 ^{Aa}	0.45 ^{Aa}	0.38 ^{Aa}	0.33 ^{Aa}	0.28 ^{Aa}	1.40 ^{Aa}	1.18 ^{Aa}	1.34 ^{Aa}	1.12 ^{Aa}	1.05 ^{Aa}	0.78 ^{Ab}
Sc4	0.50 ^{Aa}	0.44 ^{Aa}	0.43 ^{Aab}	0.41 ^{Aa}	0.36 ^{Ab}	0.33 ^{Aa}	1.49 ^{Aa}	1.10 ^{Aa}	1.36 ^{Aa}	1.12 ^{Aa}	1.04 ^{Ab}	0.89 ^{Aa}

821 Same upper and lower case letters are not significantly different at P < 0.05 among the scenarios in a column and among the years in rows, respectively according to LSD
 822 Test for separation of mean. Values are the average of three replicates (n = 3)

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825

826 Table 3. Changes in extractable cations (me L⁻¹) under different management scenarios

Scenario/ Year/ Soil depth	Na ⁺						K ⁺						Ca ²⁺						Mg ²⁺					
	2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019	
	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30
Sc1	2.68 ^{Aa}	2.86 ^{Aa}	2.57 ^{Aa}	2.14 ^{Ab}	1.49 ^{Ab}	1.7 ^{Ac}	0.14 ^{Aa}	0.17 ^{Aa}	0.1 ^{Aa}	0.14 ^{Aa}	0.17 ^{Aa}	0.11 ^{Aa}	2.63 ^{BCa}	1.42 ^{Ba}	2.00 ^{Ba}	2.04 ^{Ba}	2.13 ^{Ba}	2.04 ^{Aa}	5.04 ^{Ab}	3.71 ^{Aa}	4.25 ^{Bb}	6.88 ^{Aa}	7.75 ^{Aa}	4.25 ^{Bb}
Sc2	2.46 ^{Aa}	2.43 ^{Aa}	2.26 ^{Aa}	2.23 ^{Aa}	1.35 ^{Ab}	1.28 ^{Ab}	0.14 ^{Aa}	0.11 ^{Ba}	0.15 ^{Aa}	0.07 ^{Ba}	0.13 ^A	0.09 ^{Aa}	3.58 ^{ABa}	2.21 ^{Aa}	3.42 ^{Aa}	2.25 ^{Ba}	3.29 ^{Aa}	1.75 ^{Aa}	3.58 ^{Aa}	3.17 ^{Aa}	3.42 ^{Ba}	3.83 ^{Ba}	3.46 ^{Ba}	3.29 ^{Ba}
Sc3	2.63 ^{Aa}	2.43 ^{Aa}	2.3 ^{Aa}	2.13 ^{Aa}	1.42 ^{Ab}	1.23 ^{Ab}	0.16 ^{Aa}	0.10 ^{Ba}	0.18 ^{Aa}	0.09 ^{Ba}	0.12 ^{Aa}	0.11 ^{Aa}	2.50 ^{Ca}	2.00 ^{Ab}	3.55 ^{Aa}	3.85 ^{Aa}	3.10 ^{ABa}	1.9 ^{Ab}	4.7 ^{Aa}	3.4 ^{Aa}	4.05 ^{Ba}	2.40 ^{Ba}	3.75 ^{Ba}	2.83 ^{Ba}
Sc4	2.78 ^{Aa}	2.45 ^{Aa}	2.65 ^{Aa}	2.15 ^{Aa}	1.41 ^{Ab}	1.73 ^{Ab}	0.15 ^{Aa}	0.10 ^{Ba}	0.15 ^{Aa}	0.09 ^{Ba}	0.13 ^{Aa}	0.09 ^{Aa}	4.06 ^{Aa}	2.38 ^{Aa}	3.53 ^{Aa}	1.91 ^{Bb}	3.84 ^{Aa}	2.28 ^{Aa}	4.66 ^{Aa}	3.03 ^{Aa}	5.81 ^{Aa}	3.09 ^{Ba}	4.28 ^{Ba}	2.59 ^{Ba}

827 Same upper and lower case letters are not significantly different at P < 0.05 among the scenarios in a column and among the years in rows, respectively according to LSD

828 Test for separation of mean. Values are the average of three replicates (n = 3)

829

830 Table 4. Changes in extractable anions (me L⁻¹) under different management scenarios

Scenar io/ Year/ Soil depth	CO ₃ ²⁻						HCO ₃ ⁻						Cl ⁻						SO ₄ ²⁻					
	2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019		2010		2014		2019	
	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30	0-15	15-30
Sc1	0.67 ^{Ba}	2.17 ^{Aa}	0.50 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^{Ab}	1.33 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^A	13.79 ^{Aa}	6.68 ^{Aa}	12.46 ^{Aa}	6.46 ^{Ba}	3.75 ^{Ab}	3.04 ^{Aa}	5.54 ^{Ba}	7.37 ^{Aa}	6.01 ^{Ba}	5.74 ^{Aa}	4.48 ^{Aa}	6.43 ^{Aa}	8.1 ^{Aa}	5.19 ^{Aa}	2.07 ^C	1.69 ^B	1.59 ^{Ab}	1.79 ^{Ab}
Sc2	2.75 ^{Aa}	0.25 ^{Aa}	0.67 ^{Aa}	0.75 ^{Aa}	0.33 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^A	11.75 ^{Aa}	9.63 ^{Aa}	10.54 ^{Aa}	9.29 ^A	3.04 ^{Ab}	3.96 ^{Ab}	4.81 ^{Ba}	6.92 ^{Aa}	5.11 ^{Ba}	5.88 ^{Aa}	2.94 ^{Aa}	3.55 ^{Ab}	7.66 ^{Aa}	6.16 ^{Aa}	7.87 ^A	4.38 ^A	1.55 ^{Ab}	1.88 ^{Ab}
Sc3	0.40 ^{Ba}	1.29 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^{Aa}	0.13 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^A	10.4 ^A	6.85 ^{Ab}	13.5 ^A	12.51 ^{Aa}	2.9 ^{Ab}	3.12 ^{Ab}	5.06 ^{Bb}	5.12 ^{Ab}	9.97 ^{Aa}	7.45 ^{Aa}	3.92 ^{Ab}	4.9 ^{Ab}	7.51 ^{Aa}	4.49 ^{Aa}	8.75 ^A	4.38 ^A	2.62 ^{Aa}	1.85 ^{Aa}
Sc4	1.00 ^{Ba}	1.17 ^{Aa}	1.06 ^{Aa}	0.50 ^{Aa}	0.19 ^{Aa}	0.0 ^A	13.75 ^{Aa}	7.5 ^{Ab}	11.63 ^{Aa}	13.00 ^{Aa}	4.63 ^{Ab}	3.79 ^{Ab}	9.24 ^{Aa}	5.7 ^{Aa}	6.04 ^{Bb}	6.64 ^{Aa}	5.6 ^{Ab}	4.08 ^{Aa}	8.66 ^{Aa}	5.27 ^{Aa}	5.66 ^B	3.37 ^A	3.43 ^{Ab}	2.59 ^{Aa}

831 Same upper and lower case letters are not significantly different at P < 0.05 among the scenarios in a column and among the years in rows, respectively according to LSD

832 Test for separation of mean. Values are the average of three replicates (n = 3)

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S × Y NS NS ** NS ** NS NS NS ** NS NS NS NS NS NS NS NS *

840 ** indicates significant at <0.001, * indicates significant at <0.05 level

841 Table 7. Pearsons correlations among the soil properties irrespective of scenarios

		Correlations																
		pH ₂	EC ₂	pH _s	EC _e	Na ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	CO ₃ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	CEC	TOC	ESP	CaCO ₃	VLC	SAR
pH ₂	1																	
EC ₂	0.52**																	
pH _s	0.91**	0.52**																
EC _e	0.26	0.74**	0.20															
Na	0.60**	0.86**	0.62**	0.75**														
Ca	-0.46*	0.10	-0.33	0.38	0.07													
Mg	0.06	0.36	-0.03	0.41*	0.08	-0.01												
CO ₃	0.36	0.46*	0.22	0.54**	0.51*	0.02	0.12											
HCO ₃	0.30	0.65**	0.41*	0.73**	0.78**	0.36	0.01	0.24										
Cl	0.47*	0.52**	0.58**	0.43*	0.56**	0.25	0.01	0.04	0.63**									
SO ₄	0.25	0.66**	0.30	0.73**	0.72**	0.48*	-0.06	0.37	0.74**	0.53**								
CEC	0.74**	-0.52**	0.71**	-0.50*	-0.63**	0.02	-0.20	-0.36	-0.46*	-0.44*	-0.42*							
TOC	0.72**	-0.20	0.69**	0.09	-0.32	0.55**	0.23	-0.26	-0.05	-0.19	0.03	0.46*						
ESP	0.74**	0.38	0.67**	0.05	0.46*	-0.17	-0.09	0.18	0.15	0.41*	0.24	-0.56**	-0.63**					
CaCO ₃	-0.01	0.11	-0.01	0.22	0.23	0.03	-0.04	0.17	0.10	-0.03	0.28	-0.26	-0.08	0.00				
VLC	0.77**	-0.42*	0.74**	-0.24	-0.51*	0.51*	-0.01	-0.11	-0.38	-0.39	-0.25	0.59**	0.66**	-0.45*	-0.1			
SAR	0.57**	0.46*	0.64**	0.16	0.61**	-0.21	-0.39	0.29	0.50*	0.43*	0.28	-0.32	-0.52**	0.32	0.07	-0.39	1	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

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843 Fig. 1. Hypothesis of crop residue action in soil

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845 Fig. 2. Geographic location map of the study area

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850 Where Sc1: conventional rice-wheat system, Sc2: conventional rice-zero tillage wheat and mungbean system, Sc3: CA based rice-wheat-
851 mungbean system, Sc4: CA based maize-wheat-mungbean system

852 Error bar represents the standard error of mean. Similar lowercase letters above error bars are not statistically significant at 5% level of
853 significance between different scenarios. Similar uppercase letters are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance among the years of
854 experiment.

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862 Fig. 4. Variation in CaCO₃ and inorganic carbon content (%) in soil under different management scenarios

863 Where Sc1: conventional rice-wheat system, Sc2: conventional rice-zero tillage wheat and mungbean system, Sc3: CA based rice-wheat-
864 mungbean system, Sc4: CA based maize-wheat-mungbean system

865 Error bar represents the standard error of mean. Similar lowercase letters above error bars are not statistically significant at 5% level of
866 significance between different scenarios. Similar uppercase letters are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance among the years of
867 experiment.

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877 Fig. 5. Variation in very labile and oxidizable organic carbon content in soil under different management scenarios

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879 Where Sc1: conventional rice-wheat system, Sc2: conventional rice-zero tillage wheat and mungbean system, Sc3: CA based rice-wheat-
880 mungbean system, Sc4: CA based maize-wheat-mungbean system

881 Error bar represents the standard error of mean. Similar lowercase letters above error bars are not statistically significant at 5% level of
882 significance between different scenarios. Similar uppercase letters are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance among the years of
883 experiment.

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898 Fig. 6. Variation in total organic carbon and total carbon content in soil under different management scenarios

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900 Where Sc1: conventional rice-wheat system, Sc2: conventional rice-zero tillage wheat and mungbean system, Sc3: CA based rice-wheat-
901 mungbean system, Sc4: CA based maize-wheat-mungbean system

902 Error bar represents the standard error of mean. Similar lowercase letters above error bars are not statistically significant at 5% level of
903 significance between different scenarios. Similar uppercase letters are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance among the years of
904 experiment.

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